

A SELF-DIAGNOSTIC TECHNIQUE FOR MONITORING THE BEARING DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE AND METALLIC JOINTS

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SUMMARY: A self-diagnostic technique based on the bolt itself is presented for monitoring the bearing damage in composite and metallic joints. Bearing damage can be monitored through strain measurements using a strain gauge bonded at the bolt head. Extensive tests using a double lap bolted joint specimens were performed to verify the health monitoring technique, including the effects of the bolt clamp-up, material response, joint geometry and loading history. The results have shown that the onset and progress of the bearing damage monitored by strain measurements of the bolt were in a good agreement with AE measurements. A three-dimensional finite element analysis meant to describe the detection mechanisms is performed.

KEYWORDS: structural health monitoring, bearing damage, mechanically fastened joints.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the mechanical joining has been widely applied in aircraft structures as an effective technique when the structural components are assembled. However, the mechanical fasteners often introduce a complicated stress field near the hole in the structures. As a consequence, the mechanically fastened joints are frequent sources of failure in aircraft structures. Bearing damage may lead to reduce the stiffness, strength and load-carrying capability of the components [1-3]. Therefore, one of the most challenging for joint design is to develop systems and structures that can monitor their own structural integrity. Besides preventing catastrophic failures on-line damage detection would reduce costs by minimizing maintenance and inspection cycles [4].

In this study, the basic concept of the self-diagnostic technique based on the bolt itself for monitoring the bearing damage in composite and metallic joints used in aircraft structures is proposed [4]. Bearing damage can be detected by means of BOLT GAUGE (BG) measurement, which is using a strain gauge bonded on the bolt head. A sample of experimental joint configuration with BOLT GAUGE system is illustrated in Fig. 1. Novel design can maintain not only the peculiar geometry and function of the mechanical fastener, but more importantly, also can provide the self-diagnostic function for component damage, and it contributes to the new technical development of the low cost and simple structural health monitoring. Extensive tests using a double lap bolted composite joint specimen are performed to verify the health monitoring technique in the various joint cases. The

Fig. 1: Basic concept of BOLT GAUGE for monitoring the bearing damage in bolted joints

investigations include the effects of the bolt clamp-up, material response, joint geometry and loading history on the detection sensitivities for the bearing damage. The onset and progress of the bearing damage monitored by strain measurements of the bolt are also compared with AE (Acoustic Emission) measurements. An axial loading test and a three-dimensional finite element analysis meant to describe the detection mechanisms is performed. The behavior of bolt deformation and the stiffness degradation due to initiation and progression of the bearing damage are estimated using a continuum damage mechanics approach.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Three different material systems were selected for comparison of detection sensitivity in the present work. The baseline material for the composite specimens was IM600/QC133 with lay-up $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$; the material 2024-T4 aluminum and chromium molybdenum steel were used in the metallic specimens.

Testing setup of the double lap joint specimens has been shown in Fig. 2. The strain gauge (UFLA-03-11 Tokyo Sokki Kenkyujo Co., Ltd.) for damage detection was bonded on the surface of bolt head. A simple and highly functional measurement system using a non-contact

Fig.2: Testing setup for the double lap joint specimen

Fig. 3: Detecting damage in bolted IM600/QC133 laminate joints

electro-optical extensometer (ZIMMER Co.) was also adopted to measure the hole elongations for the bolted joint specimen, which has been developed in the authors' previous work [5].

All the tests were conducted using an INSTRON-8501 machine at room temperature. The displacement control mode was used to apply load to specimen at a cross-head speed of 1.0 mm/min. The responses such as load-displacement curve, acoustic emission and bolt strain were measured during the monotonic tensile tests and the cyclic loading-unloading tests.

DAMAGE MONITORING RESULTS

Monotonic Tensile Tests

Effect of materials

Figs. 3-5 show the BG responses and failure views tested by monotonic tensile joint test for all materials. Both the BG responses and AE measurement were compared with load-displacement curve (P- δ curve) for IM600/QC133 composites and 2024-T4 aluminum (Fig. 3-4). It was found that the significant nonlinear behavior began to appear in the load-displacement curve once damage occurred. And at same time the responses by the bolt sensor and AE sensor were also sharp changed. For Molybdenum panel, this is a special case

Fig. 4: Detecting damage in bolted 2024-T4 aluminum joints

Fig. 5: Detecting damage in bolted chromium molybdenum steel joints

with stiffening material unlike for the previous cases (Fig. 5). The main mode of bearing failure is occurred at bolt surface. Therefore, it can be found that BG also gets the information even if the bolt failed.

Effect of clamping forces

Fig. 6 shows the influence of the initial clamping torque on the bolt strain output for IM600/QC133 laminates. For all the cases, the degradation appearing in the load-displacement curve was agreement well with the damage detection measured by the bolt sensor.

Effect of joint geometries

Fig. 7 shows the influence of the joint geometry on the bolt sensor output for IM600/QC133 laminates. All the specimens with three failure modes were designed of the same of bolt diameter (d) and laminate thickness (t). The variables were considered to change the width-to-diameter ratio w/d , and edge distance-to-diameter ratio e/d . The difference of damage sensitivity for each specimen due to the joint geometry effects was shown.

Fig. 6: Comparison of GB output with various initial clamping torques tested for IM600/QC133 laminates

Fig. 7: Comparison of GB output with various joint geometries tested for IM600/QC133 laminates

Cyclic Loading-Unloading Tests

The responses of joint strength and bolt strain were measured during the cyclic loading-unloading tests, which used a displacement control mode. The strain changes as a function of the applied load for IM600/QC133 laminates and 2024-T4 aluminum are shown Fig. 8. The enveloping curve shows nearly unchanged than during monotonic tensile loading. The unloading and reloading curves, however, show a somewhat unexpected behavior than the loading, because of the relationship of permanent strain.

DETECTION MECHANISMS

Based on a past investigation [6], an important fact that the state of initiation and progression in the bearing damage can be detected through measuring the out-of-plane deformation has been found. The basic method for monitoring the bearing damage is proposed as shown in Fig. 9. Once the load P arrives at the critical damage load P_c , the microscopic space inside

Fig. 8: Strain changes obtained during the cyclic loading-unloading tests

Fig. 9: Method of BOLT GAUGE for monitoring the bearing damage

material will begin to be formed with damage progress. Consequently, the material properties will be degraded such as the Poisson ratio *etc.*, and then the through-the-thickness deformation is also increased notably. Simultaneously, as the load transfer effect, the flexural deformation at bolt head will be occurred. Therefore, the damage information can be obtained through the strain measurements on real time using a strain gauge bonded on the bolt head.

In order to understand the damage detection mechanisms by the idea of using BG measurement to monitor the bearing damage progress, two investigations were conducted as following. First, the deformation of bolt depressed was quantitatively calibrated by an axial loading test. The second investigation performs a nonlinear three-dimensional FE analysis to predict the damage response of bolted joints, and compares with measured results to examine the validity of BG measurement.

For the axial loading test, specimen that using a bolt combined a set of up-and-down block was designed; this is illustrated in Fig. 10. The responses with different clamping forces are shown in Fig. 10. It was found that the bolt depression responses are depending strongly to change of axial loading. It can be also said that the same mechanisms using BG measurements can be obtained from bolted joints.

Fig. 10: Bolt depression response during axial loading test

Fig. 11 FE model and boundary conditions

The finite element model was established with the commercial finite element package

Fig. 12 Effective elastic moduli for 2024-T4 aluminum

ABAQUS. Because of symmetry, a half of the middle lap in a double shear-lap bolted joint with one-half of the thickness of the aluminum plate was modeled (See Fig. 11). To predict the bearing damage responses in bolted aluminum plate joint, the progressive failure analysis and material degradation were performed. Because aluminum materials are highly nonlinear,

Fig. 13 Comparison between the measured and calculated BG responses

Fig. 14: Predicted bolt depression deformation, (a) $P=1.5KN$; (b) $P=4KN$; (c) $P=7KN$; (d) $P=10.5KN$

they may also exhibit different yield stresses in tension and compression. The degraded behaviors for 2024-T4 aluminum obtained from a tension test is shown in Fig. 12. With this and the effective elastic moduli can be conducted through the user subroutine USDFLD. Comparison of numerical and experiential for the 2024-T4 aluminum specimens is shown in Fig. 13. The results were found to agree well with the existing experimental data. Fig. 14 presents a series of predicted results for the bolt depression deformation under different loading stages. From the numerical results, the prediction is fairly good if the nonlinear material behavior is included in the model.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a more practical method of making BOLT GAUGE measurements has developed and tested that allows greater accessibility to the applications of the health monitoring technique to bolted joints. The results of this investigation can be summarized as follows:

1. The health monitoring technique for the bearing damage examined in this study is fully effective, during monotonic tensile tests and cyclic loading-unloading tests.
2. The detection sensitivity and functionality based on this technique that have a response level almost equivalent to AE sensor, is shown.
3. The irreversibility that appeared in the loading-unloading test needs to be evaluated for other materials.

REFERENCES

1. Xiao, Y. and Ishikawa, T.: "The Issues for Mechanically Fastened Composite Joints", 28th Symposium of JSCM, 2003, pp. 95-96.
2. Xiao, Y. and Ishikawa, T.: "Bearing Strength and Failure Behavior in Bolted Composite Joints (Part I: Experimental Investigation)", *Composites Science and Technology*, Volume 65, Issues 7-8, 2005, pp. 1022-1031.
3. Xiao, Y. and Ishikawa, T.: "Bearing Strength and Failure Behavior in Bolted

Composite Joints (Part II: Modeling and Simulation)", *Composites Science and Technology*, Volume 65, Issues 7-8, 2005, pp. 1032-1043.

4. Xiao, Y., Kakuta, Y. and Ishikawa, T.: "A Design of Intelligent Bolted Composite Joints with Damage Detection Function", Proceedings of Annual Meeting of Japan Society for Composite Materials, 2003, pp.63-64.
5. Xiao, Y. and Ishikawa, T.: "Non-contact measurement for bearing strength of mechanically fastened joints in CFRP composites", *Journal of the Japan Society of Composite Materials*, 26(6), 2000, pp. 213-218.
6. Xiao, Y. and Ishikawa, T.: "Effect of Lateral Constraint and Stacking Sequence on the Response of Bolted Composite Joints", 27th Symposium of JSCM, 2002, pp. 161-162.